

Supplemental Table S1. Descriptive data of results from a questionnaire on housing and management of milk fed calves in 170 Swedish dairy herds classified as being herds with a large proportion of primiparous cows with low SCC at first and second milk recording after calving (LL herds), a large proportion of primiparous cows with high SCC at first milk recording and low SCC at the second milk recording (HL herds) or with a large proportion of primiparous cows with high SCC at first and second milk recording after calving (HH herds). Results from the univariable multinomial logistic regression analysis are presented

Questions	LL herds	HL herds	HH herds	Total	<i>P</i> -value
Do you have an SOP ¹ for housing and movement of milk fed calves?					0.50
Yes	54	38	54	146	
No	7	8	6	21	
Do housing vary much for these heifers?					0.23
Yes	8	2	4	14	
No	54	45	56	155	
How many persons take care of these calves?					0.93
1	8	4	7	19	
2-3	43	35	44	122	
>3	12	8	9	29	
If more than one, does someone have the main responsibility?					0.84
Yes	37	27	33	97	
No	18	16	20	54	
Do you have an SOP for colostrum feeding?					0.0002
Yes	31	25	12	68	
No	31	22	48	101	
Do you have an SOP for milk feeding after the colostrum period?					0.01
Yes	29	25	16	70	
No	33	22	44	99	
Are heifer calves fed whole milk and from what source?					0.02
Yes, they are given milk from the milk in the bulk tank	23	10	11	44	
Yes, they are given milk that was not sent to the bulk tank	23	28	38	89	
No	15	8	8	31	
Are heifer calves fed milk from cows with high SCC?					0.003
Yes	29	28	46	103	
No	33	18	14	65	
Are heifer calves fed milk from cows with clinical mastitis?					0.46

Yes, during the withdrawal period after treatment with antibiotics	19	17	21	57	
Yes, during antibiotics treatment as well as withdrawal period and from cows that are not treated with antibiotics	10	6	15	31	
No	32	24	24	80	
At what age are calves weaned on average?					0.009
8–9 weeks of age	38	21	19	78	
10–11 weeks of age	13	10	13	36	
≥12 weeks of age	11	16	27	54	
Did you observe teat sucking among calves during the last 12 months?					0.02
Yes, 1-3 calves	27	24	22	73	
Yes, more than 3 calves	15	5	23	43	
No	21	18	15	54	
Is fly control used in the area of milk-fed calves?					0.06
Yes	49	41	41	131	
No	14	6	19	39	
Did any calf younger than 2 months of age have diarrhea during the last 12 months?					0.28
Yes	62	45	60	167	
No	1	2	0	3	
Estimated proportion of calves with diarrhea?					0.66
1-4%	9	4	10	23	
5-9%	16	14	14	44	
10-29%	20	18	18	56	
≥30%	16	8	18	42	
Did any calf 0-6 months of age have respiratory problems during the last 12 months?					0.21
Yes	42	32	48	122	
No	21	15	12	48	
Estimated proportion of calves with respiratory problems?					0.80
1-2%	11	8	11	30	
3-4%	9	7	6	22	
5-9%	7	7	13	27	
≥10%	25	9	18	42	
Registered ² average cleanliness score ³					0.15
3	59	43	53	155	
2	1	3	6	10	
Registered presence of diarrhea in any of the observed groups?					0.09
Yes	13	7	20	40	
No	49	37	39	125	
Registered presence of coughing in any of the observed groups?					0.26
Yes	10	11	17	38	

No	51	34	42	127	
Registered teat sucking in any of the observed groups?					
Yes	8	7	16	31	0.09
No	53	35	40	128	

¹ SOP = standard operating procedures.

² Registered by technician/veterinarian at herd visit.

³ Cleanliness score = see main text for explanation.

Supplemental Table S2. Descriptive data of results from a questionnaire about housing and management of heifers in early (first 3 months) pregnancy and about pasture of heifers in 170 Swedish dairy herds classified as being herds with a large proportion of primiparous cows with low SCC at first and second milk recording after calving (LL herds), a large proportion of primiparous cows with high SCC at first milk recording and low SCC at the second milk recording (HL herds) or a large proportion of primiparous cows with high SCC at first and second milk recording after calving (HH herds). Results from the univariable multinomial logistic regression analysis are presented

Questions	LL herds	HL herds	HH herds	Total	<i>P</i> - value
Do you have an SOP ¹ for housing and movement of heifers in early pregnancy?					0.89
Yes	51	39	48	138	
No	10	7	11	28	
Do housing vary much for these heifers?					0.48
Yes	8	9	12	29	
No	54	38	46	138	
How many persons take care of these heifers?					0.85
1	7	4	9	20	
2-3	43	32	38	113	
>3	12	11	13	36	
If more than one, does someone have the main responsibility?					0.62
Yes	31	25	33	89	
No	26	16	18	60	
Do you have an SOP for the feeding of these heifers?					0.06
Yes	24	16	12	52	
No	38	30	48	116	
Are the heifers fed corn silage?					0.59
Yes	10	11	13	34	
No	52	36	47	135	
Are the heifers fed beet pulp silage?					0.21
Yes	2	3	1	6	
No	60	44	59	163	
Did you observe teat sucking among these heifers during the last 12 months?					0.02
Yes, 1-3 heifers	21	18	32	71	
Yes, more than 3 heifers	8	1	7	16	
No	33	28	19	80	
Do you use fly control in the housing area of these heifers?					0.10
Yes	22	13	11	46	
No	40	34	49	123	

Have the heifers been ill during the last 12 months?					0.18
Yes	16	12	8	36	
No	46	34	51	131	
Registered ² average cleanliness score ³					0.30
2.5–3	47	39	42	128	
≤2	16	8	18	42	
Is stagnant water present on heifer pastures and is it enclosed?					0.95
Yes, stagnant water, but enclosed	10	10	11	31	
Yes, stagnant water, not enclosed	28	19	26	73	
No stagnant water	25	18	21	64	
Lowest age of heifers when first let out on pasture?					0.66
2-4 months	17	15	21	53	
5-6 months	35	22	25	82	
≥7 months	11	10	14	35	
Numbers of months on pasture in the first year of life?					0.08
1.5-3 months	18	6	8	32	
3.5-4 months	15	11	15	41	
4.5-5 months	25	13	20	58	
6-8 months	5	12	13	30	
Numbers of months on pasture in the second year of life?					0.007
2-4 months	9	8	0	17	
4.5-5 months	19	15	25	59	
5.5-6 months	33	18	25	76	
7-7.5 months	2	5	10	17	

¹ SOP = standard operating procedures.

² Registered by technician/veterinarian at herd visit.

³ Cleanliness score = see main text for explanation.

Supplemental Table S3. Descriptive data of results from a questionnaire about housing and management of heifers in late pregnancy (last 2 months) in 170 Swedish dairy herds classified as being herds with a large proportion of primiparous cows with low SCC at first and second milk recording after calving (LL herds), a large proportion of primiparous cows with high SCC at first milk recording and low SCC at the second milk recording (HL herds) or a large proportion of primiparous cows with high SCC at first and second milk recording after calving (HH herds). Results from the univariable multinomial logistic regression analysis are presented

Questions	LL herds	HL herds	HH herds	Total	<i>P</i> - value
Do you have an SOP ¹ for housing and movement of heifers in late pregnancy?					0.65
Yes	48	41	47	136	
No	11	6	11	28	
Do housing vary much for these heifers?					0.50
Yes	13	6	12	31	
No	49	41	48	138	
How many persons take care of these heifers?					0.87
1	8	5	4	17	
2-3	40	31	41	112	
>3	14	11	14	39	
If more than one, does someone have the main responsibility?					0.65
Yes	34	23	34	91	
No	20	19	20	59	
Do you have an SOP for feeding of these heifers?					0.03
Yes	24	22	14	60	
No	38	24	46	108	
Are the heifers fed corn silage?					0.86
Yes	14	10	11	35	
No	49	37	49	135	
Are the heifers fed beet pulp silage?					0.13
Yes	7	1	3	11	
No	55	46	56	157	
Are the heifers introduced to the lactating cow ration?					0.87
Yes, less than 3 weeks before calving	16	11	11	38	
Yes, at 3 weeks or more before calving	35	28	39	102	
No	9	7	10	26	
Are heifers kept together with lactating cows before calving?					0.004
Yes	27	30	43	100	
No	36	17	17	70	

Do the heifers go with the cows to milking/through the AMS ² ?					0.28
Yes	17	16	24	57	
No	42	31	32	105	
Are heifers kept together with dry cows before calving?					0.51
Yes, always/sometimes	41	26	34	101	
No	22	21	26	69	
Have you observed teat sucking among these heifers during the last 12 months?					0.02
Yes, in 1 - 3 heifers	9	8	21	38	
Yes, in more than 3 heifers	3	0	1	4	
No	50	39	37	126	
Is fly control used in the housing area of these heifers?					0.04
Yes	20	21	13	54	
No	41	25	45	111	
Is teat dipping/spraying used before calving?					0.09
Yes	9	2	3	14	
No	53	45	57	155	
Are the udders of these heifers examined before calving?					0.43
Yes	30	25	25	80	
No	32	21	35	88	
If yes, how many of the heifers are examined?					0.62
All	21	17	19	57	
At least half of them	4	5	2	11	
Less than half of them	4	1	3	8	
If yes, how is the udder examined?					0.05
Inspection and palpation	3	2	8	13	
Inspection	22	14	13	49	
Palpation	4	9	4	17	
Has milk leakage been observed among these heifers during the last 12 months?					0.41
Yes	13	15	17	45	
No	49	32	43	124	
Has udder oedema been observed among these heifers during the last 12 months?					0.06
Yes	16	11	25	52	
No	46	36	34	116	
Has udder-thigh lesions been observed among these heifers during the last 12 months?					0.46
Yes	22	21	28	71	
No	39	26	32	97	
Has udder cleft dermatitis been observed among these heifers during the last 12 months?					0.10
Yes	6	1	1	8	
No	55	46	59	160	
Has any of these heifers been ill during the last 12 months?					0.89
Yes	8	7	7	22	

No	54	40	53	147	
Registered ³ average cleanliness score ⁴					0.10
3	41	38	36	115	
2	18	8	20	46	
1	4	0	3	7	
Registered average hair loss score ⁴ on hocks					0.34
3	55	37	53	145	
2	5	8	6	19	
1	2	1	0	3	
Registered average skin wound score ⁴ on hocks					0.75
3	55	41	57	153	
2	4	3	2	9	
Registered average security score ⁴					0.80
3	50	40	49	139	
2	10	5	7	22	
1	1	1	0	2	

¹ SOP = standard operating procedures.

² AMS = automatic milking systems.

³ Registered by technician/veterinarian at herd visit.

⁴ See main text for explanations.

Supplemental Table S4. Descriptive data of results from a questionnaire about management of heifers/primiparous cows in the period around calving and in the colostrum period in 170 Swedish dairy herds classified as being herds with a large proportion of primiparous cows with low SCC at first and second milk recording after calving (LL herds), a large proportion of primiparous cows with high SCC at first milk recording and low SCC at the second milk recording (HL herds) or with a large proportion of primiparous cows with high SCC at first and second milk recording after calving (HH herds). Results from the univariable multinomial logistic regression analysis is presented

Variable/category	LL herds	HL herds	HH herds	Total	<i>P</i> -value
How many persons take care of these animals?					0.92
1	6	3	4	13	
2-3	42	35	44	121	
>3	15	9	12	36	
If more than one, does someone have the main responsibility?					0.73
Yes	26	23	26	75	
No	31	20	28	79	
Do the heifers calve in individual calving pens?					0.15
Yes	44	38	51	133	
No	17	9	8	34	
Is the calving area only used by heifers?					0.03
Yes	4	1	10	15	
No	57	45	47	149	
Do you have an SOP ¹ for housing of these heifers?					0.56
Yes	51	39	51	141	
No	12	8	7	27	
Do housing vary much for these heifers?					0.90
Yes	7	4	5	16	
No	56	42	55	153	
How is the calving area cleaned after every calving?					0.25
Removal of all bedding material	13	11	8	32	
Removal of all bedding material and disinfection	7	12	17	36	
Removal of all bedding material and cleaning with water	3	3	2	8	
Visible dirty parts are removed	10	5	12	27	
No cleaning or just adding new bedding material	5	1	3	9	
When is the heifer moved to the calving area?					0.51
<1 day before expected calving	7	3	8	18	
1 day before expected calving	25	22	31	78	

>1 day before expected calving	29	22	21	72	
When is the primiparous cow moved from the calving area?					0.02
<1 day after calving	16	7	8	31	
1 day after calving	24	23	26	73	
2 days after calving	18	9	10	37	
≥3 days after calving	3	8	15	26	
When is the calf taken from the primiparous cow?					0.07
As soon as possible (< 12 h after birth)	26	16	13	55	
Within 12-24 h	17	12	16	45	
Within 1-3 days	20	15	28	63	
After >3 days	0	4	3	7	
Where are primiparous cows milked during the colostrum period?					0.02
In the ordinary milking system	51	28	48	127	
In the calving area	12	19	12	43	
Are primiparous cows milked in a certain order relative to multiparous cows?					0.001
Yes	32	14	12	58	
No	30	33	48	111	
Is post-milking teat dipping/spraying used during the colostrum period?					0.67
Yes	53	37	47	137	
No	10	10	13	33	
If yes, are iodine-based products used?					0.21
Yes	20	14	25	59	
No	18	12	10	40	
Is the udder health of primiparous cows investigated during the colostrum period?					0.62
Yes	46	38	44	128	
No	17	9	15	41	
Proportion of primiparous cows with less than 4 functioning udder quarters during the last 12 months?					0.55
<1.64%	19	8	14	41	
1.65-4.58%	18	10	14	42	
4.59-7.20%	14	14	13	41	
≥7.21%	12	15	15	42	
Is any restraining method used at milking of primiparous cows?					0.001
Yes	53	27	33	113	
No	10	20	26	56	
If yes, to how many cows?					0.40
Some	48	21	30	99	
All	3	4	1	8	
Other	2	2	2	6	
If yes, how often per animal?					0.60
At all milkings	11	4	9	24	
At some milkings	30	16	20	66	
Other	8	7	4	19	

If yes, what is used?					1.00
Only kicking bow	28	13	17	58	
Only leg straps	4	2	2	8	
Fixation of head or leg by other means	11	6	7	24	
Combination of restraining methods	8	5	6	19	
Is oxytocin used to facilitate milk let down of primiparous cows?					0.12
Yes	47	28	35	110	
No	16	19	25	60	
If yes, proportion of cows treated with oxytocin?					0.91
<3.14%	29	24	32	85	
3.14-7.92%	18	11	13	42	
≥7.93%	16	12	15	43	
Is fly control used in the housing area of these animals?					0.08
Yes	27	27	22	76	
No	32	18	36	86	
Has udder oedema been observed among these animals during the last 12 months?					0.07
Yes	29	18	36	83	
No	34	29	24	87	
If yes, proportion of animals with udder oedema?					0.24
0%	34	29	24	87	
1-9%	13	8	17	38	
≥10%	15	9	18	42	
Has udder-thigh lesions been observed among these animals during the last 12 months?					0.68
Yes	45	35	47	127	
No	18	12	13	43	
If yes, proportion of animals with udder-thigh lesions?					0.76
0	18	12	13	43	
1-4%	10	7	10	27	
5-9%	14	16	19	49	
≥10%	20	10	17	47	
Has udder cleft dermatitis been observed among these animals during the last 12 months?					0.15
Yes	12	4	5	21	
No	50	43	55	148	
Has teat papilloma been observed among these animals during the last 12 months?					0.37
Yes	29	16	23	68	
No	32	30	37	99	
Has any of these animals been ill during the last 12 months?					0.72
Yes	35	22	32	89	
No	28	24	28	80	
If yes, which diseases were most common?					0.61

Mastitis	20	14	17	51	
Mastitis and other diseases	9	8	6	23	
Hoof and leg disorders	1	0	3	4	
Other diseases	4	1	4	9	
If yes, proportion of animals that have been ill?					0.48
0%	28	24	28	80	
1-4%	14	6	15	35	
≥5%	19	15	13	47	

¹ SOP = standard operating procedures.

² Registered by technician/veterinarian at herd visit.

Supplemental Table S5. Descriptive data of summarized results on housing and bedding from calf to calving from a questionnaire about management of heifers/primiparous cows in 170 Swedish dairy herds classified as being herds with a large proportion of primiparous cows with low SCC at first and second milk recording after calving (LL herds), a large proportion of primiparous cows with high SCC at first milk recording and low SCC at the second milk recording (HL herds) or a large proportion of primiparous cows with high SCC at first and second milk recording after calving (HH herds). Results from the univariable multinomial logistic regression analysis are presented

	LL herds	HL herds	HH herds	Total	P- value
Number of changes of housing system (e.g. from single to group box, from deep-bedding to slatted floor)					0.28
≤5	22	15	24	61	
6	21	11	15	47	
7	15	9	13	37	
≥8	5	12	8	25	
Are heifers ever kept on slatted floors?					0.75
Yes	17	13	20	50	
No	45	33	40	118	
Are heifer calves kept on slatted floors during the milk period?					n.a.
Yes	0	0	0	0	
No	63	46	60	169	
Are heifers kept on slatted floors during early pregnancy?					0.38
Yes	6	4	10	20	
No	55	42	50	147	
Are heifers kept on slatted floors during late pregnancy?					0.38
Yes	1	3	3	7	
No	61	43	60	161	
Are heifers kept on deep bedding during the last 2 months before calving?					0.41
Yes	17	9	11	37	
No	43	37	47	127	
Are heifers ever kept in systems without bedding?					0.49
Yes	24	13	20	57	
No	37	33	39	109	
Are heifer calves kept in systems without bedding during the milk period?					n.a.
Yes	0	0	0	0	
No	63	46	60	169	
Are heifers kept in systems without bedding during early pregnancy?					0.34
Yes	14	6	13	33	
No	45	40	47	132	

Are heifers kept in systems without bedding during late pregnancy?					0.30
Yes	9	3	5	17	
No	50	43	51	147	
Are recycled manure solids used as bedding?					0.40
Yes	1	1	0	2	
No	62	45	60	167	

Supplemental Table S6. Descriptive data of results from a questionnaire about miscellaneous factors in 170 Swedish dairy herds classified as being herds with a large proportion of primiparous cows with low SCC at first and second milk recording after calving (LL herds), a large proportion of primiparous cows with high SCC at first milk recording and low SCC at the second milk recording (HL herds) or a large proportion of primiparous cows with high SCC at first and second milk recording after calving (HH herds). Results from the univariable multinomial logistic regression analysis are presented

	LL herds	HL herds	HH herds	Total	<i>P</i> -value
Have cows been bought during the last 12 months?					0.46
Yes	3	5	3	11	
No	60	42	57	159	
Have heifers been bought during the last 12 months?					1.00
Yes	8	5	7	20	
No	55	42	53	150	
Are the calving pens also used as sick pens?					0.67
Yes, sometime	38	24	35	97	
Yes, often	5	5	8	18	
No	20	18	16	54	
Is the hair of the heifers trimmed and if so when?					0.09
Yes, before calving	7	9	17	33	
Yes, after calving	4	2	4	10	
Yes, at calving	6	12	6	24	
Yes, at housing	20	8	12	40	
Yes, when needed	1	4	2	7	
Yes, when possible	0	1	1	2	
Yes, in winter	1	3	0	4	
Yes, no time given	5	0	7	12	
No	19	8	11	38	
Have you observed contagious teat lesions in the herd?					0.10
Yes	3	0	0	3	
No	59	46	60	165	
Do not know	1	1	0	2	
Do you know which udder pathogens that are present in your herd?					0.42
Yes	56	39	50	145	
No	6	8	10	24	
If yes, which udder pathogens are most common in your herd?					-
Staphylococci, streptococci and <i>Escherichia coli</i>	10	8	21	39	
Staphylococci and <i>E. coli</i>	8	8	7	23	

Staphylococci and streptococci	6	10	7	23	
Streptococci	7	4	4	15	
Staphylococci	5	1	4	10	
Staphylococci, streptococci, <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	6	0	3	9	
Streptococci and <i>E. coli</i>	4	1	2	7	
Staphylococci, streptococci and <i>Trueperella pyogenes</i>	2	2	0	6	
<i>E. coli</i>	1	2	0	3	
Staphylococci and <i>T. pyogenes</i>	1	1	0	2	
Staphylococci, streptococci, <i>E. coli</i> , <i>Klebsiella</i> spp. and <i>T. pyogenes</i>	2	0	0	2	
<i>E. coli</i> and <i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	0	0	1	1	
<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	1	0	0	1	
<i>T. pyogenes</i>	1	0	0	1	
Staphylococci and <i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	1	0	0	1	
Staphylococci, <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	1	0	0	1	
Staphylococci, streptococci, <i>E. coli</i> and <i>T. pyogenes</i>	0	1	0	1	
Streptococci, <i>E. coli</i> and <i>T. pyogenes</i>	0	1	0	1	
Streptococci, <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	1	0	0	1	
Staphylococci, streptococci and enterococci	0	0	1	1	
The farmer mentioned <i>E. coli</i>					0.37
Yes	33	21	34	88	
No	23	18	16	57	
The farmer mentioned <i>Klebsiella</i> spp.					<0.001
Yes	12	0	4	16	
No	44	39	46	129	
The farmer mentioned staphylococci					0.28
Yes	42	31	43	116	
No	15	8	7	30	
The farmer mentioned streptococci					0.55
Yes	38	26	38	102	
No	18	13	12	43	
The farmer mentioned <i>T. pyogenes</i>					0.007
Yes	6	5	0	11	
No	50	34	50	134	
Which type/s of staphylococci is/are most common in your herd?					0.01
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	29	20	31	80	
<i>S. aureus</i> and other staphylococci ¹	12	4	7	23	
Other staphylococci	0	6	3	9	
Which type/s of streptococci is/are most common in your herd?					0.51
<i>Streptococcus dysgalactiae</i>	6	5	4	15	
<i>Str. dysgalactiae</i> and <i>Streptococcus uberis</i>	9	1	5	15	

<i>Str. uberis</i>	6	2	6	14	
<i>Streptococcus agalactiae</i>	2	2	2	6	
<i>Str. agalactiae</i> , <i>Str. dysgalactiae</i> and <i>Str. uberis</i>	0	1	2	3	
<i>Str. agalactiae</i> and <i>Str. dysgalactiae</i>	1	0	0	1	
<i>Str. agalactiae</i> and <i>Str. uberis</i>	0	0	1	1	
Are the lactating cows milked according to udder health status?					<0.001
Yes	32	9	14	55	
No	31	38	46	115	
Is ViLa ² used on the farm?					0.88
Yes	10	6	8	24	
No	53	41	52	146	

¹ Other staphylococci = most likely non-aureus staphylococci.

² ViLA = a herd program supervised by a field veterinarian when the farmer can use some pharmaceutical drugs for treatment of some diseases (e.g. mastitis).

Supplemental Table S7. Descriptive herd data on health, fertility and culling in 170 Swedish dairy herds classified as being herds with a large proportion of primiparous cows with low SCC at first and second milk recording after calving (LL herds), a large proportion of primiparous cows with high SCC at first milk recording and low SCC at the second milk recording (HL herds) or a large proportion of primiparous cows with high SCC at first and second milk recording after calving (HH herds). Results from the univariable multinomial logistic regression analysis are presented

	LL herds	HL herds	HH herds	Total	<i>P</i> -value
Annual proportion of deaths of calves <24h of age of total number of born calves					1.00
<3.2	16	12	14	42	
3.2-4.6	17	12	13	42	
4.7-6.9	15	11	16	42	
>6.9	15	12	15	42	
Annual mortality/culling rate for heifer calves 1-59 days old per 100 heifer calves 1-59 days old-days					0.12
0	39	23	22	84	
2.4-4.8	12	13	17	42	
>4.8	12	11	19	42	
Annual mortality/culling rate for heifer calves 60–179 days old per 100 heifer calves 60–179 days old-days					0.24
0	50	37	39	126	
≥2.7	13	10	19	42	
Annual mortality/culling rate for heifers 6-15 months old per 100 heifer 6-15 months old-days					0.62
0	48	37	41	126	
≥1.9	15	10	17	42	
Annual incidence rate of veterinary treated cases of clinical mastitis per 100 cow-days					0.72
<3.7	12	11	18	41	
3.7-8.4	17	11	13	41	
8.5-15.2	15	12	14	41	
>15.2	19	12	11	41	
Annual incidence rate of veterinary treated cases of clinical hoof or leg diseases/injuries per 100 cow-days					0.24
0	29	23	30	82	
1.6-4.2	16	8	17	41	
>4.2	18	15	9	42	
Annual incidence rate of cases of hoof or leg diseases/injuries registered by hoof trimmers per 100 cow-days					0.21

<3.1	12	16	13	41	
3.1-10.6	18	7	16	41	
10.7-22.5	19	8	14	41	
>22.5	14	15	13	42	
Annual incidence rate of veterinary treated cases of paresis and hypomagnesemia per 100 cow-days					0.51
<1.19	21	9	11	41	
1.19-2.5	14	10	17	41	
2.6-4.3	13	13	15	41	
>4.3	15	14	13	42	
Annual incidence rate of veterinary treated cases of clinical feeding associated disorders per 100 cow-days					0.08
0	37	15	30	82	
0.64-1.8	13	14	14	41	
>1.8	13	17	12	42	
Annual incidence rate of veterinary treated cases of clinical diseases per 100 cow-days					0.10
<11.7	15	7	19	41	
11.7-20.3	14	17	10	41	
20.4-31.1	14	10	17	41	
>31.1	20	12	10	42	
Annual culling rate of cows per 100 cow-days					0.31
<28.9	17	14	11	42	
28.9-34.0	11	15	16	42	
34.1-39.6	16	11	15	42	
>39.6	19	7	16	42	
Annual culling rate due to fertility disorders per 100 cow-days					0.99
<4.3	16	13	13	42	
4.3-7.0	17	11	14	42	
7.1-9.7	15	11	16	42	
>9.7	15	12	15	42	
Annual culling rate due to udder health disorders per 100 cow-days					<0.001
<5.2	19	15	8	42	
5.2-7.8	9	15	18	42	
7.9-11.9	10	12	20	42	
>11.9	25	5	12	42	
Annual culling rate due to hoof and leg disorders per 100 cow-days					0.62
<0.81	11	15	16	42	
0.8-2.2	16	11	15	42	
2.3-4.2	18	9	15	42	
>4.2	18	12	12	42	
Mortality rate of cows per 100 cow-days					0.81
<2.9	13	13	16	42	

2.9-4.8	16	11	15	42	
4.9-7.3	14	13	15	42	
>7.3	20	10	12	42	
Annual culling rate of primiparous cows 1-90 days after calving per 100 primiparous cow-days					0.92
0	30	26	27	84	
3.2-5.8	16	11	15	42	
>5.8	16	10	16	42	
Incidence rate of heifers not inseminated at 17 months of age or older per 100 heifer-days					0.18
<7.7	22	10	10	42	
7.7-15.9	16	14	12	42	
16.0-32.0	12	10	20	42	
>32.0	13	13	16	42	
Proportion of cows with difficult calvings out of total number of calvings					0.85
<0.6	19	12	11	42	
0.6-1.5	16	11	15	42	
1.6-2.6	15	11	16	42	
>2.6	13	13	16	42	
Proportion of cows with more than 70 days between calving and first insemination out of total number of cows inseminated					0.40
<12.5	17	10	15	42	
12.5-18.4	12	17	13	42	
18.5-25.4	15	9	18	42	
>25.4	19	11	12	42	
Proportion of cows with more than 120 days between calving and last insemination out of total number of cows inseminated					0.91
<4.5	17	9	16	42	
4.5-5.8	16	13	13	42	
5.9-7.6	15	11	16	42	
>7.6	15	14	13	42	
Calving interval					0.41
<12.4 months	18	8	16	42	
12.4-12.8 months	13	14	15	42	
12.9-13.4 months	19	9	14	42	
>13.4 months	13	16	13	42	
Age at first calving					0.03
<25.5 months	23	13	6	42	
25.5-26.5 months	13	13	16	42	
26.6-27.9 months	16	10	16	42	
>27.9 months	11	11	20	42	